

THE ROLE OF SURFACE ANALYSIS IN UNDERSTANDING THE INTERFACIAL CHEMISTRY ASSOCIATED WITH THE USE OF ADHESION PROMOTERS

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ABSTRACT

Organosilanes are widely used in a variety of applications to enhance the strength and durability of organic/inorganic interfaces. Many examples can be taken from engineering structures such as high performance fibre reinforced polymeric composites and adhesive bonding of metallic structure for aerospace and other applications. Surface analysis methods such as X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) and time of flight secondary ion mass spectrometry (ToF-SIMS) have an important role to play in the understanding of the interfacial chemistry associated with such applications, and this paper provides an overview of such investigations with examples from the use of γ -GPS for the structural adhesive bonding of aluminium.

To obtain a better understanding of interaction mechanisms occurring within the adhesive/silane/metal joint, we investigated the interfacial chemistry of silane and epoxy-based adhesives. All analyses were carried out using XPS and ToF-SIMS. Initial work was carried out by the study of the interaction of an analogue molecule of an amine cured adhesive (diethanolamine) with the GPS coated aluminium substrates. The interaction between a commercial dry film adhesive and GPS treated aluminium substrates was also examined. The results have established that there is formation of covalent bonds at the silane/adhesive interface. This type of bonding is very important to an adhesively bonded joint because it is not susceptible to aqueous attack.

INTRODUCTION

In the structural adhesive bonding of aluminium, a pre-treatment is required to ensure good durability. The accepted method is the use of acid anodising processes but for environmental reasons an alternative is now being sought. In particular, a procedure involving the application of a 1% aqueous solution of γ -glycidoxy propyl trimethoxy silane (GPS) adhesion promoter on aluminium, followed by drying at an elevated temperature has been shown to have much to commend it for repair purposes. Although the use of such a pre-treatment method does, undoubtedly, produce strong joints with good durability, there has been much discussion in the literature as to the source of the improved hydrodynamic stability. The use of organosilanes as adhesion promoters (in the case of metals) is based on the assumption of a specific interaction between the oxidised metal surface and the silane in use. This is achieved by the formation of a covalent bond via condensation between hydroxyls present at the surface of the metal and silanols of the silane [1]. Although this is a theoretical prediction and it has indeed been proven on iron and steel [2, 3], there is still very little experimental evidence of this interaction on aluminium [4, 5]. It has been shown previously that the logical manner to approach such an investigation is to use secondary ion mass spectrometry (SIMS) as it has the necessary surface sensitivity and ability to identify specific and

characteristic molecular fragments. The region of the positive spectrum of interest, ca $m/z = 71$, yields many fragments including those arising from hydrolyzed GPS or even hydrocarbon contamination. Consequently, the unambiguous identification of an Al-O-Si⁺ fragment can only be achieved with the current generation of high mass resolution time-of-flight analysers providing both very high mass resolution and analyser transmission. This paper reports the interaction between GPS and oxidised aluminium using ToF-SIMS at sufficiently high resolution to unambiguously resolve the question of Al-O-Si⁺ existence. The application of an epoxy or other adhesives with such a pretreatment layer is of prime importance for the aerospace industry. To mimic the interaction of an epoxy resin adhesive with an organosilane primer, it is possible to use more simple molecules than the resin itself which present some similar characteristics. Amine-cured epoxy resins are formed from the linkage of multifunctional amines with epoxides. This produces a linkage containing an hydroxyl group in a position β to an amine group. Therefore, diethanolamine (DEA) was chosen as it contains an hydroxyl group in β to an amine group and two alcohol functionalities. As a follow-up to this work, a real formulated adhesive was adsorbed onto GPS coated aluminium and its interactions with the primer layer studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials and methods.

Aluminium sheets of commercial purity (>98%) were supplied by Goodfellows. Samples were prepared following an industrial procedure. This consisted in degreasing the aluminium using detergent and tap water, then grit blasting after drying with fresh alumina grit (50 microns). Samples were punched to disks of 1 cm diameter and subsequently degreased in an acetone or isopropanol. They were then brushed for 2 minutes with a 1% aqueous solution of γ -glycidoxy propyl trimethoxy silane or GPS (OSi Silquest, product designation A187) that had been hydrolysed for 60 minutes (full hydrolysis) in MilliQ water. The samples were dried in an oven at 93°C for 60 minutes. Some of the samples were also treated with in solutions of diethanolamine, HO(CH₂)₂NH(CH₂)₂OH (DEA) at 0.01M or 0.5M in absolute ethanol for 30 seconds. They were then rinsed in absolute ethanol for 5 seconds and let to dry in air for at least half an hour. The treatment of samples with the adhesive solution was performed at various concentrations of a fraction of an epoxy adhesive in the liquid form. This was obtained by dissolution in toluene of the solid adhesive.

X-ray photoelectron Spectrometry (XPS) analysis.

XPS analyses were carried out using a VG Scientific ESCALAB MKII system operated in the constant analyser energy mode. Mg K α source was used and the pass energy was set at 50 eV with a take-off angle at 45°. The area of analysis was 5x2 mm². Digital acquisition was achieved with a VGS 5000S data system based on a DEC PDP11/73 computer interfaced to the spectrometer. The following spectra were acquired: Survey spectrum, C1s, O1s, N1s, Si2p, SiKLL, Al2p and Na1s. The manufacturer's data processing software allowed smoothing linear and Shirley background removal, peak-fitting and quantification. Some of the data reported here were also recorded on a Thermo VG Scientific SigmaProbe spectrometer using monochromated AlK α radiation with a 400 mm spot size and 100W power. Spectrum processing was carried out using the computer software, *Avantage v1.77*. The pass energy was set at 100 eV for the survey scan and 20 eV for the high resolution windows.

ToF-SIMS analysis.

The analysis has been performed on ToF-SIMS VG type 23 system equipped with a double-stage reflectron time of flight analyser and a MIG300PB pulsed liquid metal source. Static SIMS conditions

were used (i.e. not more than 10^{13} ions/s/analysis) with a pulsed (10 kHz and 30 ns) 20 keV $^{69}\text{Ga}^+$ primary ion beam rastered over a frame area of 1 mm^2 at 50 frames.s^{-1} . SIMS spectra were recorded in the mass range of m/z 5-600 in both positive and negative ion modes. The high resolution mass spectra were obtained from a Physical Electronics PHI 7200 TOF/SALI system equipped with a reflectron time of flight analyser pulsed liquid metal source. Static SIMS conditions were used: pulsed (5 kHz and ca. 1 ns) 8 keV $^{133}\text{Cs}^+$ primary ion beam over an area of $250\times 250\text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$. SIMS spectra were recorded in the mass range of m/z 5-1000 in both positive and negative ion modes. Data recorded on the ToF-SIMS IV were obtained in a similar manner (25 kV, static conditions, $^{69}\text{Ga}^+$ source) but the spectrum presented was recorded on a region of $20\times 20\text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$ which in itself is indicative on the capabilities of this last generation instrument.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Specific interaction of GPS with aluminium surface.

Building a parallel with previous work [2, 3] a fragment indicative of a specific interaction is thought to have the structure Al-O-Si^+ of mass 71 similar to that found for iron at $m/z=100$ for the structure Fe-O-Si^+ . The Fragments obtained at high resolution mass spectroscopy for the nominal mass 71 are shown in Table 1 with their respective assignments and possible structures (data from the experiment performed on the PHI 7200 instrument). Figure 1 shows the spectrum in the region of nominal mass $m/z = 71$ (spectra recorded on the ToF SIMS IV instrument).

The precision given in ppm is calculated as follows:

$$\Delta = \frac{|M_{\text{exp.}} - M_r|}{M_r} < 1 >$$

where $M_{\text{exp.}}$ is the experimental mass obtained from the high mass resolution spectrum and M_r is the real mass calculated from exact masses. The attribution of a specific structure and/or formula is thought to be correct when Δ is less than 50 ppm which is the case for almost all fragments presented here. The first fragment is indicative of a specific interaction between the aluminium substrate and the GPS layer. All other fragments except the second, third and last are thought to arise from the GPS coating. The last fragment is indicative of some hydrocarbon contamination as GPS does not contain any hydrocarbon chain any longer than three carbons. This contamination can arise from the outer layer of the material but also from a slight contamination during the process. Two different structures are likely for the third fragment but we chose to attribute the first structure listed as the Δ is very small. This structure is not likely to occur from the hydrolysed GPS, it is thought to arise from initial contamination of the chemical from by-products of the synthesis reactions.

Specific interaction of DEA with GPS and/or aluminium.

After examination of the SIMS spectra obtained in the positive mode of aluminium treated with GPS and DEA or treated with DEA only, it was found that DEA adsorbs readily on both aluminium and aluminium treated with GPS. This is indicated by numerous fragments exhibiting an even mass. This is a special feature of spectra arising from samples coated with nitrogen containing molecules. These fragments and other characteristic are given in Table 2 with their assignments.

Table 1: Fragments obtained at nominal mass 71 and their respective assignments

Experimental mass (amu)	Exact mass (amu) [6],	$ \Delta $ (ppm)	Assignments
70.9552	70.95334	25	AlOSi^+
70.9781	70.9773	11	Si_2CH_3^+
70.9933	70.9953	29	$\text{SiOC}_2\text{H}_3^+$
71.0117	71.0133	22	$\text{C}_3\text{H}_3\text{O}_2^+$
71.0512	71.0497	21	$\text{C}_4\text{H}_7\text{O}^+$
71.0886	71.0861	36	$\text{C}_5\text{H}_{11}^+$

Figure 1: Spectra at high resolution of grit-blasted aluminium coated with GPS at nominal mass $m/z = 71$.

Most fragments can arise from DEA fragmentation such as those at $m/z = 40, 42, 56, 58, 62, 70, 74, 86, 88$. Nevertheless, some other masses are present in the spectra at higher than expected the molecular mass of DEA. It was concluded that masses are obtained because of condensation of DEA in a dimer of mass 192. This can explain the presence of such peaks as those at $m/z = 98, 100, 116, 118$. We noticed the presence of a particular fragment at higher masses: $m/z = 247$ (see Figure 2 and 3). This fragment is present only when hydrolysed GPS is adsorbed prior to any DEA deposition. This, together with the increase of fragments 142 and 144 (originate from fragmentation of fragment 247) seem to indicate a specific interaction of DEA with hydrolysed GPS. A mechanism of interaction similar to that which occurs for crosslinking in the bulk of an epoxy resin is expected. In these experiments, it occurs between the last carbon of the epoxy ring and the unshared pair of electrons on one nitrogen of the DEA dimer, which leads to a structure of mass 247, this being confirmed by the high resolution mass spectroscopy (not shown here).

Table 2: Fragments obtained in the positive ToF-SIMS spectrum and formulae for samples treated with DEA

Fragment mass (m/z)	Assignment
23	Na ⁺
27	Al ⁺ /C ₂ H ₃ ⁺
28	Si ⁺ /CO ⁺ /CHNH ⁺ /AlH ⁺
30	CH ₂ NH ₂ ⁺
40	Ca ⁺ /C ₂ N ₂ H ₂ ⁺
45	SiOH ⁺
56	C ₃ NH ₆ ⁺
58	C ₃ NH ₈ ⁺ /C ₂ NOH ₄ ⁺
62	C ₂ NOH ₈ ⁺
70	C ₄ NH ₈ ⁺
74	C ₄ NH ₁₂ ⁺
86	C ₄ NOH ₈ ⁺
88	C ₄ NOH ₁₀ ⁺
98	C ₅ NOH ₈ ⁺
100	C ₅ NOH ₁₀ ⁺
106	C ₄ NO ₂ H ₁₂ ⁺
116	C ₅ NO ₂ H ₁₀ ⁺
118	C ₅ NO ₂ H ₁₂ ⁺
142	C ₇ NO ₂ H ₁₂ ⁺
144	C ₇ NO ₂ H ₁₄ ⁺
247	C ₁₁ N ₂ O ₄ H ₂₃ ⁺

Another peak was observed at m/z=106 amu for all samples, on both GPS treated and untreated Al. As it is not present in the spectrum of pure DEA deposited on platinum, this peak is evidence of a specific interaction of DEA with either GPS and/or aluminium. It is attributed to totally or partially protonated DEA. The presence of the 106 amu peak can be explained by a hydrogen bond type of interaction between DEA and silanol from GPS or from hydroxyl sites present at the aluminium surface and DEA. The two types of specific interactions described above are supported by the high resolution N1s XPS for both types of samples treated with DEA (not shown here). The signal can be peak fitted with two peaks, the binding energies indicate for the first peak a neutral type of nitrogen involved in three bonds, the second one is explained by the presence of a quaternary nitrogen (401.7 eV) involved in a bond with either a carbon or a hydrogen hence the protonation.

Specific interaction of epoxy adhesive with GPS and/or aluminium.

Samples of aluminium were also treated with the epoxy adhesive solution (in toluene). Sample codes are as follows: sample 1, grit-blasted only; samples 2 to 6, aluminium coated with the solution with concentrations ranging from 0.01% to 1% w/w; sample 6 coated with GPS primer; samples 7 to 12, coated with GPS then adhesive solutions in the same range of concentrations. The surface concentrations are reported in Table 3.

Some of the elements present such as sodium and calcium result from cross-contamination from the grit used for the blasting. The signal of nitrogen appears only when any sample is treated with the adhesive solution. It may originate from either a crosslinking agent or a catalyst contained within the resin to cure the adhesive as it is known that the commercial resin used in this work is based on an epoxy resin [7]. The surface composition for all the examined samples is presented in Table 3 below. For clarity, the concentrations of calcium and sodium have been omitted as they vary only slightly (between 0.1 and 2.5

at. %) and because their respective concentrations decrease with application of GPS and /or adsorption of the adhesive.

Figure 2: SIMS spectra of respectively (a) grit-blasted aluminium treated with 0.5M DEA, (b) Grit-blasted aluminium treated with GPS only and 0.5M DEA

The very low carbon concentration on the sample grit-blasted only (sample 1) together with high concentrations of oxygen and aluminium indicates a very clean surface. In all cases, the adsorption of organic material is shown by an increase of the carbon concentration. The intensity of nitrogen indicative of the curing agent and/or catalyst is increasing with the concentration of the adhesive in solution. It is also very noticeable that the concentrations of carbon and nitrogen are either significantly or slightly more intense when GPS is deposited first which indicates a better interaction of the main components of the adhesive when the aluminium is coated with the GPS primer.

The examination of the SIMS spectra recorded in the positive mode of detection indicated the presence of several ions of even mass together with ions characteristic of diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA), a precursor of epoxy resins. Even ions are very characteristic of fragments containing an odd number of nitrogen ions, e.g. 1 or 3, as the nitrogen atom is trivalent.

Figure 3: Schematic of reaction between DEA dimer and GPS layer onto aluminium

Table 3: XPS surface composition for all samples treated with adhesive solution

Sample	C	O	Al	Si	N
1	14.3	60.6	20.4	1.7	NA
2	35.7	44.3	16.6	1.3	0.7
3	37.6	47.4	11.6	1.1	1.2
4	48.9	36.0	12.4	0.9	1.1
5	57.4	28.7	10.3	0.9	1.9
6	54.9	31.3	10.4	1.1	1.7
7	21.3	56.5	16.0	3.9	0.8
8	35.3	47.4	11.3	4.6	0.8
9	51.9	35.5	6.5	4.4	1.2
10	51.1	35.9	7.6	3.2	1.7
11	52.9	34.0	7.9	2.5	2.1
12	60.1	29.4	5.6	2.4	2.2

The main positive fragments are resumed in Table 4 with their structure assignment. One particular feature was observed at the mass $m/z = 277$ Da. This fragment suggests an interaction that explains and confirms how the adhesive bonds to the GPS adhesion promoter. The presence of this cluster ion also implies that the bond formed is of covalent nature and therefore very strong and durable. It should be noted that this ion is not as intense when no GPS is used. As it is nevertheless present when the adhesive is solely adsorbed on aluminium, it may be assumed that the interaction occurs via the epoxy end of the main resin or the GPS silane. This ion can then be either a demonstration of the covalent bond formation between GPS and the adhesive or partial crosslinking within the resin. Figure 3 presents an example for the mass region 270 to 290 Daltons.

Although not presented here, the data illustrating the interaction or adsorption of the adhesive on both substrates were fitted to a Langmuir type of equation which indicates that a monolayer of material has been adsorbed.

Figure 3: Positive spectrum ($m/z = 270$ to 290 Da.) for (a) grit-blasted aluminium treated with GPS only, and (b) grit-blasted aluminium treated with GPS and 1 % (w/w) adhesive.

CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown with the use of surface sensitive techniques such as XPS and SIMS that several types of interactions can occur in a joint. In the case of GPS on aluminium, the ultimate evidence has been given to demonstrate that a covalent bond is formed between the silanol of hydrolysed GPS and the oxidised aluminium surface. This is in agreement with the chemical theory of organosilane adhesion promoters. In the case of DEA experiments it was shown that DEA can interact in two ways on GPS: with the formation of a covalent bond and hydrogen bond. The latter also occurs for DEA interacting on aluminium. The covalent bond formed is obtained via the interaction of GPS epoxy ring opening and the lone pair of electron of DEA.

Surface analyses experiments have been performed on thin adhesive films deposited on either GPS coated aluminium or grit-blasted aluminium by both XPS and ToF-SIMS. It was shown that the adhesive adsorbs more on a GPS coated surface, evidence of a better interaction. Studies of the films by ToF-SIMS reinforce this conclusion with the presence of a mass feature present at $m/z = 277$ Da indicative of the formation of a covalent bond between either the epoxy group of the adhesive and the curing agent or the GPS and curing agent. Figure 4 shows a schematic of the anticipated reaction leading to the fragmentation of a ion at $m/z = 277$.

Figure 4: Reaction between GPS and curing agent leading to $m/z = 277$. The same type of reaction is expected between DGEBA (main component of the adhesive) and the curing agent

Table 4: Main fragments from the adhesive coating in the positive spectrum

Nominal mass (m/z)	Formula	Assignment
26	CN ⁺	⁺ C≡N
30	CNH ₄ ⁺	CH ₂ =NH ₂ ⁺
42	C ₂ NH ₄ ⁺	CH ₂ =N=CH ₂ ⁺
44	C ₂ H ₆ N ⁺	CH ₂ =C=NH ₂ ⁺
57	C ₃ H ₅ O ⁺	CH ₃ -CH=NH ₂ ⁺
58	C ₂ H ₄ NO ⁺	H ₂ C-C-CH ₂ ⁺ O
72	C ₃ H ₆ NO ⁺	⁺ O≡C-NH-CH ₃
77	C ₆ H ₅ ⁺	
91	C ₇ H ₇ ⁺	
128	C ₁₀ H ₈ ⁺	
135	C ₉ H ₁₁ O ⁺	
178	C ₁₃ H ₉ ⁺	
191	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ ⁺	

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